

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Mamatova Maxmuda Yorqinjon qizi

SHEKSPIRNING “HAMLET” ASARI HAQIDA

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

